

SUPPLEMENT 1. Colors referred to in the descriptions.

Nos.	Samples	Color names		Color codes
		Chinese	English	
\		瓷白色	ceramic white	#FEFEFA
\		蒜黄色	garlic yellow	#F1F0D4
\		油橙色	butter orange	#F2DF8F
\		锈橙色	rust orange	#D79A65
\		木乃伊红色	mummy red	#994D2E
\		草黄色	thatch yellow	#F1ECC5
\		污黄铜褐色	dirty brass brown	#B47F5A
\		巧克力褐色	chocolate brown	#86604B
\		檀香褐色	sandal brown	#BA8B70
\		铜橙色	copper orange	#A56B34
\		犀牛褐色	rhinoceros brown	#DBC299
\		羊毛白色	merino white	#F9F5EC